

WELL-BEING OF STUDENTS OF URBAN AND RURAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS AT HIGH LEVEL OF AUTONOMY

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to find out relationship of autonomy and well-being of secondary school students. The sample consists of 999 secondary school students (495 urban and 504 rural students) from various schools of two districts of Punjab (Ludhiana and Moga). Autonomy was assessed with the help of Adolescent Autonomy Inventory (AAI) by Kumar, and Malik, 2015 and well-being was assessed with the help of Personal wellbeing scale developed by Sujatha and Taj (2019). The results revealed that there exists a significant and positive correlation between well-being and autonomy (high level) among students of both urban and rural secondary schools.

Key words: *Autonomy, Well-being, Secondary school students, Rural, Urban, High level*

Introduction

After childhood he/she enters the adolescence stage. Adolescence marks the transitional phase from childhood to adulthood. In this study investigator conducted the research work to assess the adolescents of secondary schools. Secondary school students their families, friends, peers, as well as society at large face both possibilities and problems as a result of the numerous social, emotional, intellectual, and physical changes that occur throughout this time. When a student enters the secondary school phase, starts taking decisions by himself/ herself. His/ her dependence on parents keeps on reducing day by day and he/she starts taking charge of his/her life, it eventually leads to secondary school students developing a sense of autonomy. Grotevant and Cooper (1985) associate the development of personal autonomy with two kinds of

processes: on the one hand, the self-affirmation (gaining self-confidence and responsibility), on the other the separation process as opposition to others. Relationships between parents and children reveal opportunities for a child to balance their unique identities and work with their parents as a foundation for developing autonomy as they grow up. Children in secondary school who have close, loving relationships involving parents who support and care for them not only show greater independence in their decision-making as well as self-expression, but they also start possessing psychological maturity, academic proficiency, and improved wellbeing. They feel more self-assured and are less likely to engage in aberrant conduct and despair as a result. Both parents and students in secondary school are active in changing the bond between parents and children without destroying the current relationships; nonetheless, the growth of autonomy is a result of the parents' image changing from an ideal to a real one.

Autonomy

Autonomy refers to a secondary school student's growing ability to think, feel, arrive at a favourable judgement and take independent action. However, the growth of autonomy does not stop when a person completes secondary school; rather, it continues to grow throughout adulthood whenever they are expected to act with a newfound feeling of independence. Through the preteen and adolescent years, autonomy assumes a particular significance as it denotes that a student at secondary school is progressively growing more self-reliant and less reliant on parents and other adults, which actually is the ultimate aim and result of perfect parental upbringing and schooling to enable him/her lead a successful life.

Types of autonomy Basically, four types of autonomy have been mainly recognized, which are attributable to secondary school students are described as follows:-

Types of Autonomy

(i) Emotional Autonomy: It enables a student to be conscious of one's own feelings, emotions, and the manner in which one relates to the people in one's immediate environment. During the secondary school phase, the mindset of young people changes from relying solely on their parents to receiving emotional support in numerous ways from friends, neighbors, family, teachers, school counselors, and others. Youth begin to see their parents probably for the first time in the form of "real" people with their strengths and weaknesses by observing their actions and ignoring their words of mouth. Now parents are no longer their ideals, the facade of blind hero worship starts to switch off. Students in secondary school are now more active in establishing friendships and starting to get to know their friends on

a more personal level. It is evident that emotionally independent secondary school students are better equipped to solve problems or seek support from peers and adults outside of their immediate family rather than relying solely on their parents. At this point, students of secondary school start to exercise their emotional independence from their parents' influence. They have developed the habit of depending more on their friends, instructors, school counsellors, and classmates than on their parents. Middle school years are when this stage begins. Students grow more independent and less reliant on parental guidance as they progress through secondary school. Due to its relational and effective significance for secondary school students' well-being, the emotional dimension can be predicted. One indicator of this puberty stage is emotional independence from parents. This is most likely due to the student's perception that their parents essentially urge them to follow their views. Students in secondary school have an innate drive to preserve an emotion that might be referred to as emotional autonomy. According to them, this is a general feeling of confidence in one's own choices and attainable goals. The term "emotional autonomy" (Steinberg and Silverberg, 1986) has a negative connotation, and is usually understood to mean a lack of attachment to one's parents, other family members, and, in rare cases, friends.

(ii) Attitudinal autonomy has been recognized as an inborn attribute among secondary school students. It is so inborn that they need not to acquire it by the power invested in professional associations or other administrative bodies. A cognitive element found in attitudinal autonomy can be discovered by looking at the mental processes of:

- a) Weighing the options
- b) and having a strong desire to accomplish something
- c) Cultivating individual values such as independence, self-control, aggressiveness, etc.
- d) Defining personal goals from their own point of view, no matter what resources are actually available.

These elements culminate into what is termed as attitudinal autonomy. It has been described as the capacity to list multiple possibilities, reach a decision, and establish an objective that one aspires to accomplish. This form of attitudinal autonomy is closely related to the concepts of:

- a) Capabilities One possesses
- b) Attitudinal independence (Hoffman, 1984)
- c) Goal setting (Markus and Wurf, 1987)

d) Reflection upon preferences and ultimate choices

e) Wishes and desires (Dworkin, 1988)

f) Decision making ability

g) Personal goals (Allen, Porter, McFarland, McElhaney, and Marsh, 2007)

(iii) Functional autonomy:- Perceptions of competence and control are examples of regulatory mechanisms that are integrated into functional autonomy. Perception of competence refers to achieving a goal, while perception of control refers to the capacity to select a certain approach for success. It influences a secondary school student's sense of responsibility and provides an incentive for his/her behavior. One definition of functional autonomy is "the capacity to devise a plan to accomplish one's objectives." It has been shown in the ideas of cognitive readiness for action and functional independence (Hoffman, 1984).

(iv) Value autonomy refers to secondary school students' independent attitudes and convictions regarding politics, morality, and spirituality. A secondary school student's capacity for abstract thought aids in their ability to distinguish between general and particular circumstances. They are able to use their higher level heightened thinking abilities to create decisions. When secondary school students develop value autonomy, they reflect on their own set of values. In this way, people have a tendency to independently determine their values, which serve as the driving force behind all of their actions. They now have a personal value framework to adhere to rather than just accepting the values their parents instilled in them or even those that their peers like. Autonomy has been defined by numerous developmental theorists in a variety of ways, including as an individual trait (Ryan, 1995), a feature of a secondary school student's relationship with others, or a reaction to their interactions with others (Freud, 1958). While some definitions highlight their independence from the limitations of childhood reliance, others concentrate on their autonomy to choose and pursue particular personal objectives (Hill and Holmbeck, 1986).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Steinberg and Silverberg (1986) explored the developments in autonomy in the early stages of adolescence, compared to boys, girls were exhibited to be more independent. Additionally, girls demonstrated strong opposition to the influence of friends in neutral and antisocial contexts. Teenagers who have greater emotional independence from their parents are less likely to act antisocially with their classmates. Daddies (2011) found that the teens were less concerned with moral and conventional issues and more interested in gaining more autonomy over personal and diverse matters. In contrast to the older adolescents, particularly the boys, the

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younger adolescents, particularly the girls, wanted more autonomy. Teenagers were more likely to want more control over complex and prudent matters if they thought their friends had more autonomy than they did. To corroborate the finding that adolescents use their peers as benchmarks to determine the proper pace of behavioral autonomy development, a second study with 170 early adolescents was carried out. Bureau and Mageau (2014), in their study of teenage honesty, highlighted the importance of parental autonomy support. According to the study's findings, teenagers who receive parental autonomy support are more honest (dimension of well-being), but those who receive controlled parenting are less honest. Duineveld, Parker, Ryan, Ciarrochi, and Salmela-Aro (2017) found that subjective support for parental autonomy was positively correlated with self-esteem, a measure of wellbeing, and negatively correlated with depressed symptoms. Only the high school and post-high transitions to school shown effects on self-esteem, however the results for the consequences on symptoms of depression were constant across all three transitions. There was evidence of coregulation for depression symptoms during the high school and post-high school transitions, and it was discovered that depressive symptoms prior to the transfer reduced autonomy support following the move. Importantly, the impacts on depressed symptoms increased as kids grew older, indicating the importance of parents even when they enter high school and enter adulthood. The autonomy of mothers and parents was equally and positively affected. Raising, Braam, Brunwasser, Jansseus, Creemers, and Scholte (2019), onset of symptoms of depression and anxiety in teenagers was negatively correlated with parental emotional support. Furthermore, it was indicated that depression symptoms as well as respect for autonomy are positively correlated among teenagers who exhibit higher degrees of parental psychosocial issue symptoms. De-Juanas, Romero, and Going (2020) explored a strong and favorable correlation between the EDATVA scale and practically every category on the Psychological Well-Being Scale. The EDATVA scale revealed moderate connections between self-organization and the Psychological Well Being Scale's control of the environment ($r = 0.447$; $p = 0.01$) as well as life purpose ($r = 0.568$; $p = 0.01$). On the other hand, context awareness on the EDATVA scale and autonomy on Ryff's scale showed the strongest link ($r = 0.382$; $p = 0.01$). Subsequent research showed that the older 18–21 age group outperformed the younger 16–17 age group on the Psychological Well-Being Scale and the EDATVA in every dimension. Jung, Hwang, Kim, Sin, Zhao, Zhang, and Park (2020) concluded that, in both nations, there is an indirect relationship between autonomy support and students' wellbeing through mother child relationships. It also demonstrated a positive correlation between mother-child connections and

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autonomy support and children's well-being. Kleinkorres, Stang-Rabrig, & McElvany, (2023) found that satisfaction with school, enjoyment of school, and self-rated health decreased over time, while social integration remained stable. Perceived teacher autonomy support also declined between Grades 5 and 9. Furthermore, baseline levels of perceived teacher autonomy support and facets of well-being were positively related. Finally and most importantly, results indicated that changes in perceived teacher autonomy support were positively associated with the development of satisfaction with school, enjoyment of school, and self-rated health, but not social integration. The findings suggest that perceived teacher autonomy support plays an important role in the development of students' well-being in adolescence phase.

Results of the study conducted by Slemp, Field, Ryan, Forner, Van den Broeck, & Lewis, (2024) indicated that supports for autonomy, competence, and relatedness were strongly positively related with the satisfaction of these basic needs and strongly negatively related to their frustration. Interpersonal supports for basic needs were strongly positively related with subjective well-being and exhibited small to moderate positive associations with performance. Moderation analyses showed general stability of effects across cultures, although correlations of autonomy support to autonomous motivation weakened as a function of individualism. The opposite pattern was observed for the correlation between relatedness support and intrinsic motivation. Competence and relatedness-supportive behaviors explained incremental variance in basic need satisfaction even after controlling for the more established effects of autonomy support. In addition, lateral need supports explained incremental variance in basic need satisfaction after controlling for vertical sources of support. According to Trigueros, & García-Mas, (2025) frustration of basic psychological needs (FBN) (physical and psychological well-being) was positively related to less self-determined motivational regulations (dimension of autonomy), while it was negatively related to grit, resilience and more self-determined motivational regulations.

Significance of this research

Keeping in mind the review of related literature, the aim of the present study was to investigate autonomy and well-being of secondary school students from two districts of Punjab (Ludhiana and Moga). The present study is important because the trends for autonomy and well-being of secondary school students for urban and rural locale show a variation. The study aims to examine autonomy and well-being of secondary school students with respect to locale.

Objectives of the study

1. To compare the relationship of well-being of students of secondary schools of urban areas at high level of autonomy.
2. To compare the relationship of well-being of students of secondary schools of rural areas at high level of autonomy.

Hypotheses

1. There exists no significant relationship in the well-being of students of secondary schools of urban areas at high level of autonomy
2. There exists no significant relationship in the well-being of students of secondary schools of rural areas at high level of autonomy.

Delimitations

1. The present study was confined to two districts of Punjab (Ludhiana and Moga).
2. The present study was confined to students of urban and rural secondary schools affiliated to Punjab School Education Board only.

Method

Sample

The sample for the study was comprised of 999 secondary school students of Punjab School Education Board from schools of two districts of Punjab (Ludhiana and Moga).

Procedure of the study

In the present study, the investigator used multi-stage randomization technique to collect the sample of study. The quantitative data was analyzed with the help of different statistical techniques i.e. mean, mode, median, standards deviation, skewness, kurtosis, Karl Pearsons coefficient of correlation.

Tools used

1. Adolescent Autonomy Inventory (AAI) by Kumar, and Malik, 2015
2. Personal wellbeing scale by Sujatha, and Taj, 2019

Statistical Techniques

1. Descriptive statistics- mean, median, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis was used to examine the nature of distribution of scores.
2. Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation technique was used to find out the relation between autonomy and well-being.

Data Analysis: Results Interpretation

The aim of the study was to find out the correlation of well-being at high level autonomy of secondary school students in regard to locale. In order to prove the formulated hypotheses, the collected data has been tabulated and discussed as under: -

DISTRIBUTION OF SCORES

To determine whether or not the condition of basic assumption implied in some of the statistical techniques employed here was met, it was desirable to describe the nature of distribution of scores of autonomy, and adolescents' well-being before presenting the actual analysis of data and discussion of results pertaining to the hypotheses.

Table 1: Nature of distribution of data for Autonomy (N=999)

Category	Mean	Median	Mode	S.D.	Skewness	Kurtosis
Autonomy	69.32	70	71	7.23	-0.282	0.690

Table 1 indicates that the mean, median, and mode of the autonomy scores are, respectively, 69.32, 70, and 71. The three central tendency measurements are fairly close to one another, indicating that the distribution is fairly close to normal. In autonomy, the standard deviation is 7.23. The distribution is negatively skewed and platykurtic in autonomy, as indicated by the values of skewness and kurtosis, which are -0.282 and 0.690, respectively. The data can be regarded as normal because of the minimal distortion.

Table 2: Coefficient of correlation between well-being of urban secondary school students at high level of autonomy (N=495)

Variables	r
Well-being and Autonomy (high)	0.148**

** correlation is significant at the 0.01 as well as 0.05 level

Relationship between urban secondary school students' well-being at high level of autonomy. Table 2 makes it clear that there is a significant and positive relationship between the well-being of students of urban secondary schools at high level of autonomy. The correlations of 0.148 was found to be significant at the 0.01 level with $df=494$. Well-being possesses a positive and significant correlation with high level of autonomy among students of urban secondary schools, indicating that autonomy is important for these students' overall wellbeing. The fact that most families in today's metropolitan environment are nuclear and both parents have to

spend most of their time at work place. Due to their hectic schedules and the fact that they spend most of their time alone at home, urban secondary school students tend to make decisions without parental approval and thereby become independent, which increases their level of autonomy. In this sense, their wellbeing is greatly influenced by high level of autonomy. Consequently, hypothesis 1, “There exists no significant relationship in the well-being of students of secondary schools of urban areas at high level of autonomy” stands rejected. Our study's findings are consistent with those of De-Juanas, Romero, and Goings's (2020) investigation, which found a strong and positive correlation between psychological well being and autonomy.

Table 3: Coefficient of correlation between well-being of rural secondary school students at high level of autonomy (N= 504)

Variables	r
Well-being and high level of autonomy	0.198**

** correlation is significant at the 0.01 and 0.05 level

Relationship between well-being of rural secondary school students at high level of autonomy. Table 3 makes it clear that there is a significant and positive relationship between the well-being of students of rural secondary schools with high level of autonomy, as seen by the correlation of 0.198, which is significant at the 0.01 level with $df=494$. However, Positive relationship shows that high level of autonomy is important for rural secondary school students' well-being. The likely cause of this relationship could be that, in the rapidly evolving lifestyles of today's population, rural areas offer the basic amenities that make up a good life (according to Maslow's need hierarchy theory, these necessities are crucial for maintaining happiness and contentment in life). Thus, a high degree of autonomy is important for the well-being of secondary school students in rural areas. Thus, the hypothesis 2, “There exists no significant relationship in the well-being of students of secondary schools of rural areas at high level of autonomy,” stands rejected.

Findings

Findings of descriptive analysis

In order to check the normalcy of distribution of scores, values of mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis are examined related to the variables of autonomy and well-being. Findings of distribution showed that scores of secondary school students for both the variables are found to be normally distributed.

Findings of correlational analysis

There is a significant and positive correlation between well-being and high level of autonomy of students of urban secondary schools. There is a significant and positive correlation between well-being and high level of autonomy of students of rural secondary schools.

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